

Appendix C — Student-Authored Report (Full Text)

Reproduced as written by the Erdkinder students of Blue Blocks, with minor spelling corrections only.

The Trip to Flipside

On 12th of March, in Hyderabad — Blueblocks decided to go to Flipside — a cloud kitchen run by neurodivergent adults. The students were divided into two groups — learning how the cloud kitchen works with the adults.

Previously we — Erdkinders ran our own venture known as Terra Utopia — now we had the opportunity to learn from others who experienced entrepreneurship already. We had hoped to learn how a group of neurodivergent people were able to run a successful cloud kitchen and what necessary inputs are needed to become this successful in this space.

Some of the interesting observations include — the fact that they had spaces for emotions — where they would tame their emotions and confidence — which shows mental strength is the backbone to building successful ventures.

Speaking of mental health — everyone of them spend 15 mins walking in sunlight — on grass, barefoot. All these factors keeps the adults sane and productive.

Some of the things we have learned from the trip include:

Neurodiverse people might need special attention but they are proof — you can achieve anything you want with passion.

When you keep your mental health sane you can always make progress in life.

Even neurodivergent people deserve a place in society.

Overall the experience was a great learning for all of us — because now we understand what we need for the venture and would always welcome Flipside to Blueblocks for more.